

INTERFACE MICROSTRUCTURE OF A DOUBLE-POURED AL/AL-5CU BIMETALLIC COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

Aluminium is a commonly used metal which has high strength to weight ratio. Recent legislations regarding limitations in the CO₂ emissions demand the development of more efficient vehicles with lower energy consumption while remaining competitive. These are main drivers within several industrial sectors for using lighter components based on Al alloys where heavier alloys have been used so far. For a component made of a single material, it is very difficult to meet various requirements such as high strength at elevated temperatures, good corrosion resistance, low price, etc. Therefore, bimetallic composites consisting of two alloys/composites are being developed where an alloy/composite is usually bonded to a substrate using different processing methods, such as rolling bonding [1] and extrusion [2].

Components with complex geometries may not be produced using the above approaches, as most works reported in literature so far only focus on the fabrication of bimetallic plates, rods, or other shape-limited products. One of the possible ways to produce bimetallic composites with complex shapes is casting. It is noted that casting one metal on to or around the base metal allows more geometric flexibility of the final products and the use of casting may reduce industrial expenses and increase productivity. However, only few works reported on this potential.

A major scientific interest for casting Al based bimetallic composites is the interface behaviour between two Al alloys. It is known that an oxide layer rapidly forms on the surface of Al in contact with air [3]. The chemically and thermally stable oxide layer acts as a diffusion barrier. Metallic bonding may be achieved when the oxide layers have either been dissolved or disrupted between two metals.

Sahm and Guentner [4] firstly studied a multi-pouring method to produce graded Al composites reinforced with SiC particles. In this method, slurries of different alloys compositions were poured into a mould sequentially. They discovered that the gradation across the interface strongly depends on the solid fraction of the first cast alloy before pouring of the second alloy. However, they did not identify the significant influence of the oxide layer formation on the interface microstructure.

This paper reports the study of the feasibility of casting an Al bimetallic composite using a similar approach and a detailed investigation of the bonding mechanism and the oxide layer evolution during processing. The approach termed as “*double-pouring*” has been used to attempt casting an Al/Al-5wt.% copper (Al/Al-5Cu for simplicity) bimetallic composite and its interface microstructure has been characterized by means of metallographic, optical microscopy (OM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX).

2 Experimental

2.1 Double pouring approach

Slugs of pure Al (~99.99%) and Al-5Cu binary alloy were initially melted and isothermally held inside two cylindrical alumina crucibles separately at 750 °C in an electric resistance furnace. After the top solid dross layer had been skimmed, liquid Al-5Cu was then poured steadily into a cylindrical graphite mould (height: 80 mm; diameter: 40 mm) which had been preheated to a certain temperature. Once Al-5Cu was partially solidified to the mushy zone, liquid Al was filled gradually on top of the Al-5Cu. The casted bimetallic composite was then air cooled to room temperature.

2.2 Microstructural characterisation

The interface microstructure of the bi-metallic composite was characterized using a variety of methods. Optical microscopy was conducted using a Zeiss microscope with Axiovision v4.8.2 software for examining the microstructures before and after etching. Both the cross-section surface and fracture surfaces of tensile bars (carefully machined to obtain the interface in the middle) were characterized, as shown by Fig. 1. Samples were prepared by grinding down to 4000 grit size SiC paper and then polishing to 1 μ m diamond suspension. Samples were observed using a JEOL SEM 840A at an operating voltage at 15kV or 20kV and using a probe current of 1~3nA. Both Secondary electron imaging (SEI) and backscattered electron imaging (BEI) modes were used. SEI gives the topographical information while BEI shows contrast between areas with different chemical compositions. Heavy elements (high atomic number, Cu), backscatter electrons more strongly than light elements (low atomic number, Al), and thus appear brighter in BEI. Therefore, both BEI and SEI were taken for each local position analyzed. The EDX analysis was performed using an accelerating voltage of 15kV, a beam current of 3nA and an acquisition time of 80 seconds for each point scan analysis.

Metallographic etching is a standard method for revealing the large-scale structure of metals and alloys by etching a properly prepared sample surface (cross-section). The samples were grounded using silicon carbide paper (down to 2500 grit size) with lubricant water and immersed into methanol solution to remove any grease, oil or other residue which may cause uneven attack to the surface. The etchant used during the study is Keller's reagent (95 ml H₂O, 2.5 ml HNO₃, 1.5 ml HCl, and 1.0 ml HF). Samples were swabbed with the etchant and the progress of etching was closely watched and etching stopped until preferred structural details were revealed.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Cross-section

3.1.1 Bonded interface

A local region with bonded interface morphology between Al and Al-5Cu was observed after etching, as shown in Fig. 2. This stitched image from multiple OM micrographs suggests metallic bonding was achieved between the Al and the Al-5Cu after

the processing. It was also found that the Al-5Cu showed much quicker response to the etchant than the Al. This is because the presence of θ -CuAl₂ phase at the grain boundaries causes rapid grain boundary corrosion during the etching process [5]. The degree of mixing between the Al and the Al-5Cu could therefore be assessed qualitatively by the optical contrast between the Cu-rich zone and the Cu-lacking zone. The width of the bond zone is estimated to be around 100 μ m according to the Fig. 2. Fig. 3 is a BEI image showing the well-bonded interface morphology between Al and Al-5Cu. As shown in the Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, the Cu gradation behavior within the α -Al matrix across the interface from the Al-5Cu side to the Al side was assessed using a EDX line scan analysis. From the result, the Cu composition within the Al matrix decreases from 1% to 0% across the interface from the Al-5Cu side to the Al side. It was found that the result could be best fitted by a sigmoid logistic function [6]:

$$y = \frac{y_0}{1 + \exp[k \cdot (x - x_c)]} \quad (1)$$

This function is usually used to describe the span (bond zone) and the gradient of an "S-shape" curve. Where y_0 is the concentration of Cu in α -Al matrix on the Al-5Cu side far away from the bond zone, k is a factor indicating the width of bond zone, x is the relative distance to zero point and x_c is the relative position of the interface to zero point. In this case, fitted results are shown in the table 1:

	value	error
y_0 (%)	0.9855	0.0046
k	0.0591	0.0017
x_c (μ m)	177.031	0.6965
Adj. R-square	0.99955	

Table 1: Fitted value of parameters.

From Fig. 4, the width of the bond zone is calculated to be around 120 μ m, similar to the result obtained from the OM image analysis. It is expected that the value y_0 shall not be equal to 5% as the segregation of Cu at cell boundaries (usually in the form of CuAl₂) causes the depletion of Cu in the centre of a cell. As shown in Fig. 3, the other EDX line scan was performed to assess gradient of Cu from the centre of a cell to an adjacent cell across the cell boundary. The result is shown in Fig. 5. The scanned Cu composition profile was well fitted with a Gauss Function, suggesting the diffusion nature of Cu from high compositions to low compositions.

3.1.2 Un-bonded interface

Un-bonded interface morphology with “crack-like” oxide film defects sandwiched between Al and Al-5Cu was also observed microscopically. According to Fig. 6, oxide film defects were observed at the interface. These oxide film defects prevent any metallic bonding between Al and Al-5Cu. This would suggest that 100% metallic bonding was not achieved through the double-pouring approach. It is because that either liquid Al or semi-solid Al-5Cu would be coated with a naturally-formed oxide layer before getting in contact. Metallic bonding is therefore only achieved when these oxide films are disrupted under sufficient mechanical agitation which allows the direct contact between fresh metals. Interestingly, it is noted that metal could be entrapped within a folded oxide film, as indicated by the red arrow in Fig. 6, suggesting the folding nature of oxide films during casting. Air, inclusion or melt is usually enveloped in a folded oxide film (bi-film) pocket.

The oxide film defects align discontinuously at the interface and they were identified as oxide bi-film defects [3, 7]. According to Fig. 7, the non-planar unbonded interface morphology with the presence of the “crack-like” bi-film defect with entrapped air is recognized, indicating the easy-to-deform nature of such oxide defect. These defects could also exist at grain boundaries or interdendritic regions in castings [7].

3.1.4 Solid fraction

The solid fraction f_s of the Al-5Cu was found to have an effect on the morphology of the bond interface, as shown by Fig. 8. As the hot liquid Al (750°C) was casted closely in contact with the solidified Al-5Cu, it would increase the local temperature of the Al-5Cu even up to its melting point through intensive heat exchange and the top surface area of solidified Al-5Cu become liquid again. The liquid melt mixing contributes to the bonding of the two metals. For example, first, when liquid Al was poured onto liquid Al-5Cu, the result would be a total mixing of two metals. Subsequently, pouring liquid Al onto the partially solidified Al-5Cu would lead to a partial re-melting of Al-5Cu and therefore a non-planar bond interface microstructure is achieved. Thirdly, when liquid Al is poured onto fully solidified Al-5Cu, the result may be a slightly partial re-melting of Al-5Cu

(depending on local temperatures) and the degree of mixing is limited. The value of f_s was estimated as a function of temperature using the Scheil-Gulliver model [8]:

$$f_s = 1 - \left\{ \frac{(T_m - T)}{m_l C_0} \right\}^{\frac{-1}{1-k}} \quad (2)$$

Where T_m is the melting point of pure solvent, m_l is the slope of liquidus line, C_0 is the starting composition of the alloy, k is the partition coefficient. This model is used to describe the solute distribution during the solidification of the alloy. As a non-equilibrium model, it assumes that solute does not diffuse back into the solid and there is a complete mixing of solute in the liquid due to convection [8]. This model also predicts that the grain boundaries are usually rich in solute as they come from the last drops of liquid. As the results shown in Fig. 9, the lever rule predicts that there is no liquid phase at the eutectic temperature (548°C) and the alloy becomes fully solid at around 570°C while the Scheil model predicts that the solid fraction is 0.92 when the alloy just reaches the eutectic temperature. When the eutectic phase transformation is over, the alloy becomes fully sold.

3.2 Fracture surfaces

SEM/EDX study on fracture surfaces confirmed the presence of oxide bi-film defects at the interface and these defects act as easy crack propagation paths. During the fracture process, a bi-film defect at the interface was split into two halves on both sides, as confirmed by the pairs of the butterfly symmetric images in Fig. 10. These defects at the bond interface are points of stress concentration and detrimental to the bond strength. According the Fig. 12 (in particular S1), the presence of Cu (2.49%) suggests a bonding is achieved between Al and Al-5Cu via liquid mixing, not by diffusion.

3.3 Bonding mechanism

As shown in Fig. 11, the bonding mechanism is proposed as follows. Initially, each metal will be coated with a thin layer of oxide. Secondly, hot liquid Al will increase the local temperature at the interface and the liquid (Al)/semi-solid (Al-5Cu) interface is pushed down as a result of partial re-melting of Al-5Cu. Thirdly, severe turbulence and thermal convection help disrupt and rupture the oxide into small pieces in the form of bi-films defects which are discontinuously distributed along

the bond interface. Therefore, 100% metallic bond is not possible due to the presence of bi-films which prevent any metallic bonding. During the fracture analysis, these defects are subject to stress concentration and bi-film defects are split into two halves, as shown by Fig. 13.

3.4 Suggestions for improved bonding

The obstacle to achieve a 100% metallic bonding is the presence of oxide films defects. Although it is impossible to prevent the oxide formation in practice, methods of disrupting these oxide films could be undertaken to minimize the influence.

First of all, as the processing time is short enough (a few minutes) and the oxide film formed on the melt would still be soft in nature, applying a pressure during the solidification may help stitch the bi-film defects by introducing adequate plastic deformation of the oxides and this will in turn increase the effective metallic bonding area. A durable bi-metal joint could be built through such method.

In addition, a previous work by the authors [9] reports a result on how a controlled induction stirring pattern re-distribute oxide bi-film defects to the top surface due to their buoyancy in the melt. This may be used to improve the bond structure by relocating the bi-films defects from the interface to the surface, as shown in the Fig. 14.

4 Conclusions

An Al/Al-5wt% Cu bimetallic composite was produced using a double-pouring casting approach. Metallic bonding was achieved through liquid metal mixing. Oxide bi-films defects formed during casting aligned discontinuously at the interface. The morphology of interface is affected significantly by the processing parameters.

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Fig. 1: Sketch of the 3-D characterization principle of the Al/Al-5Cu composite.

Fig. 2: A stitched image from multiple OM micrographs showing the well-bonded interface morphology between Al and Al-5Cu. OM micrographs were taken after the cross-section had been etched.

Fig. 3: Backscattered electron image (BEI) showing the well-bonded interface morphology. Red dotted lines are two EDX line scan paths (Vertical: Scan across the bond interface; Horizontal: Scan from a centre of the cell to the adjacent cell)

Fig. 4: Plot of the EDX line scan showing the Cu gradation within the α -Al matrix across the interface from the Al-5Cu side to the Al side.

Fig. 5: Composition profile showing the variation of Cu from the centre of a cell to an adjacent cell across the cell boundary.

Fig. 6: OM image showing the unbonded morphology of the interface.

Fig. 7: BEI image showing the interface microstructure.

Fig. 8: Graph showing the influence of the solid fraction of the first cast Al-5Cu on the final Al/Al-5Cu bimetallic interface microstructure morphology.

Fig. 9: Plots showing solid fraction of Al-5Cu as a function of temperature.

Fig. 10: Pairs of SEI (top two) and BEI (bottom two) images showing the fracture surfaces morphology on both Al side and the Al-5Cu side. All micrographs were taken at the same magnification.

Fig. 11: Schematic diagram showing the bonding mechanism between Al and Al-5Cu during a double-pouring casting process.

Fig. 12: EDX spectrum and calculated showing the different oxygen composition in different positions. Analysis was performed on the Al side fracture surface.

Fig. 13 Schematic diagram showing the fracture mechanism of a double-poured Al/Al-5Cu.

Fig. 14. Suggestions of downstream processing methods for double-pouring approach.

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